

From the Desk of Editor in Chief

**Birth of new journal dedicated to serve medical justice
system, IJMJ**

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International Journal of Medical Justice, IJMJ is an official publication of GLAFIMS ACADEMY. GLAFIMS is abbreviation of the Global Academy of Forensic and Investigative Medicine and Science. This is a collection of likeminded people involved in Forensic Medicine, Forensic Sciences, Investigative Forensic Medicine, Law Persons, Investigative Authorities and Persons, Forensic Pathologists, and allied sciences. The Main aim of the association is to collaborate and cooperate with each other for the academic and professional development by enhancing mutual interactions. GLAFIMS Association is registered with Government of India.

At present, International Journal of Medical Justice [IJMJ] publishes two issues per year in June [January-June Issue] and December [July-December Issue]. Special Issues of the journal publication may be published based on the collective wisdom of the Editorial Board. The Editor-in-Chief/Editor reserves the right to notify the proceeding of the Editorial Board. The International Journal of Medical Justice [IJMJ] publishes original research, peer-reviewed observational, experimental, and clinical studies, meta-analyses, review articles, case reports and invited reviews in the fields of medicine and allied subjects. Apart from this journal also entertains conference paper, unpublished data, letter to the editor etc subject to being accepted by the editorial board. Papers deemed accepted for publication must meet all the criteria of originality, priority, scientific actuality. All the submitted papers will go through rigorous review process.

All the manuscript will be returned to the corresponding author in case not following the submission guidelines even without reviewing. The decision of Editor in Chief, IJMJ will be final in all respects. Editor in Chief/Editor reserves the right to reject the manuscript if they are of the opinion that the paper is not suitable for the publication/review.

The International Journal of Medical Justice, IJMJ aims to provide a common platform for publishing/sharing good quality of research in the field of Forensic Medicine, Investigative Medicine, Medical Toxicology, and allied specialties such as Law, Justice, Nursing Sciences etc. The focus thus shall primarily be toward Medical Justice.

Medical Justice consists of two terms medical sciences and criminal justice administration. It's a collaborative concept between medicine, science and law. The various medicine and science specialties which are more often applied to facilitate the legal as well as the criminal justice administration are broad focus of medical justice.

Forensic Medicine is application of medicine in the court of law, similarly, any part of medical science or science which is applied to facilitate the legal system comes under the category of medical justice. Allied forensic medicine and science specialities include Law and Justice, Forensic Nursing etc are part of Medical Justice System.

Very often it is difficult to separate out these specialities which work with each other side by side to facilitate the criminal justice administration system. In this journal we will mainly publish that which is directly or indirectly around the philosophy of "Medical Justice".

The International Journal of Medical Justice [IJMJ] will publish original research, peer-reviewed observational, experimental and clinical studies, meta-analyses, review articles, case reports and invited reviews in the fields of Forensic Medicine, Forensic Sciences, Investigative Forensic Medicine, Law Persons, Investigative Authorities and Persons, Forensic Pathologists and allied sciences.

As per policy of the International Journal of Medical Justice, IJMJ we follows the ICMJE's Recommendations for the Conduct, Reporting, Editing and Publication of Scholarly Work in Medical Journals and have voluntarily adopted policies prepared by the WAME Ethics and Policy Committee (formerly the Publication Ethics and Editorial Policy Committees).

As signatory of BOAI20: THE BUDAPEST OPEN ACCESS INITIATIVE Declaration, IJMJ is committed to open access by supporting institutional self-archiving and/or open-access-journals.

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